

FEATURES OF MOTIVATION FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITIES OF STUDENTS OF DIFFERENT EDUCATIONAL FIELDS

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Annotation. Professional activity determines a person's professional self-awareness and professional orientation. This article examines the features of professional motivation of students studying in different areas.

Keywords. Professional activity, professional self-awareness and orientation, motivation of professional activity of representatives of various educational spheres.

Annotasiya. Kasbiy faoliyat shaxsning kasbiy o'zini o'zi anglashi va kasbiy yo'nalganligini belgilaydi. Ushbu maqolada turli yo'nalishlarida tahsil oluvchi talabalarning kasbiy faoliyat motivasiyasining o'ziga xos jihatlari o'rganib chiqildi.

Kalit so'zlar. Kasbiy faoliyat, kasbiy o'z o'zini anglashi va yo'nalganligi, turli ta'lim soha vakillarining kasbiy faoliyat motivasiyasi.

Аннотация. Профессиональная деятельность определяет профессиональное самосознание и профессиональную направленность человека. В данной статье изучены особенности профессиональной мотивации студентов, обучающихся по разным направлениям.

Ключевые слова. Профессиональная деятельность, профессиональное самосознание и направленность, мотивация профессиональной деятельности представителей различных образовательных сфер.

In the modern work environment, specialists are required everywhere, but it must be recognized that not all people who have worked for a long time and well in a certain profession or specialty have the necessary professionalism.

In the next decade, the problems of professional skills became a subject of close consideration in psychology (E.A. Klimov, A.K. Markova, L.M. Mitina, Yu. P. Povarenkov, etc.) [1, 2, 3, 4]. Researches devoted to professional activities, professional requirements, professional selection and training (works of V.A. Bodrov, E.F. Zer, Yu. K. Strelkov, etc.) appeared in labor psychology and related fields of psychology. But in most cases, researchers limit themselves to the study of a set of professional qualities - important professional qualities, their formation and evaluation. It is not entirely clear what a person psychologically means as a subject of professional activity, how the master of his work differs

mentally from other people who are considered only professional workers. It should be recognized that the task of revealing the psychological mechanisms of the formation and development of human professional skills has not yet been solved.

According to V.A. Bodrov, professional self-determination can be considered a multi-dimensional and multi-stage process and can be seen from different perspectives:

- as a series of tasks that society sets before an individual and how to find a solution to it:

- as a step-by-step decision-making process, through which a person balances his desires,

- the interests, goals and requirements of labor activity, needs of societies, etc.;

- as a process of formation of a professional person, assessment of his individual style and actions [5]

N. S. Pryajnikov believes that the main (ideal) goal of a professional is the client's internal independent readiness and conscious planning, adjustment and realization of his development (professional, life and personal) [6].

With the intention of analyzing the specific aspects of the characteristics of professional activity motivation among students studying in different fields of education, we conducted a study and found out the existence of a number of differences in the level of confidence (Table 1).

Table 1

The results of the study of the dependence of the characteristics of students' professional activity motivation on the fields of education (Kruskal-Wallis H-criterion)

Indicators	Average colors			H	p
	Social and humanitarian sciences (N=1256)	Natural sciences (N=152)	Exact Sciences (N=363)		
Internal motivation	866,8	1047,0	882,5	17,2	0,000**
Positive external motivation	861,7	1050,3	901,3	19,1	0,000**
Negative external motivation	881,4	850,5	916,9	2,2	0,330

Note: ** - $p < 0.01$

In the analysis of the internal motivation scale, it was found that there are differences in the level of confidence ($H=17.2$; $p<0.01$). The superiority of internal motivation is a set of behaviors that our test takers understand. The superiority of internal motivation was noted for the students of the natural direction. It is typical for them to understand each activity and have ideas about why they are studying here. The lowest result was recorded in the indicators of students studying in the social and humanitarian field, and their lagging behind the students of natural sciences in realizing their desires is clearly visible. In fact, from our many observations in the process of pedagogical activity, it is known that if students in the field of natural sciences are given a task, they try to do it seriously, but when tasks are given to students studying in the social and humanitarian field, they often have a superficial approach to completing these tasks. is noticeable. They do not understand why they are given this task, they only blindly and superficially perform tasks, and sometimes even when explaining certain tasks to representatives of the humanitarian sector, they do not try enough to understand the real essence of the problem.

Figure 2.3.4. The results of the study of the dependence of the characteristics of students' professional activity motivation on the fields of education (Kruskal-Wallis H-criterion).

In the analysis of the scale of positive external motivation, it was found that there are differences in the level of confidence ($H=17.2$; $p<0.01$). Positive extrinsic motivation is based on activities aimed at satisfying other needs, that is, it is reflected as circumstances unrelated to the activity. We can observe that

the performance of students in the field of natural sciences prevails in this scale as well.

In the analysis of the negative extrinsic motivation scale, no differences in the level of confidence were found ($H=2.2$; $p>0.05$). This result can serve as a basis for concluding that external negative motivation does not depend on which direction students study.

Summarizing the above-mentioned analytical data, it can be concluded that the study areas of students have a direct impact on their internal and external motivation.

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